

Available at: www.ijlsas.com
2024, Vol: 6, Issue:2,33-49

The role of plant growth-promoting microbes (PGPMs) in the solubilization of Zinc

Navendra Uniyal¹, Bhawana Dhami², Himani Petwal², Sakshi Verma² and Avinash Sharma ^{1*}

¹Department of life science, Monad University, Kastala Kasmabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

²Doon Groups of Institutions, Shyampur, Rishikesh

Corresponding author: navendraunniyal121@gmail.com

Received:23-08-2024

Accepted: 09-10-2024

Abstract

The rising population of the world needs more food which is dependent on agricultural production. Farmers saturate fields with a variety of agrochemicals in indiscriminate amounts to enhance productivity per unit of time per unit area to meet this demand. Generally, most of the nutrients are supplied to plants using fertilizers. However, micronutrients are ignored and zinc (Zn) is one of those that aren't primarily responsible for increasing yield. Zn is an essential micronutrient necessary for the growth of all living organisms, including humans, plants, and microbes. Humans and other living organisms need trace amounts of Zn in their bodies for normal physiological functioning. Most of the agricultural soil are either Zn deficient or have Zn in a fixed form that is unavailable to plants, indicating a Zn deficit in both soils and plants. Therefore, to address the issue mentioned above, alternative, and environmentally friendly technologies are needed, such as the application of plant growth-promoting microorganisms (PGPMs) which increase Zn

solubilization and plant availability. PGPMs are important for the survival of plants because these microorganisms provide essential nutrients to plants from the soil.

Keywords: Agriculture, nutrients, soil, environment, plant growth

Introduction

Zinc (Zn) is an essential element for the survival of cells, and deficiencies in this element lead to various metabolic disorders that present themselves in a wide range of diseases in humans (Gibson, 2006). The low solubility of Zn in soil is one of the main reasons behind the phenomenon of Zn deficit in crops (Cakmak, 2008). Plants cannot absorb insoluble forms of Zn found in soil, such as smithsonite, sphalerite, znite, franklinite, willemite, and hopeite (Rehman et al., 2021). Insufficient Zn not only prevents crops from growing but also reduces the amount of Zn in agricultural production, lowering their nutritional value and ultimately causing Zn deficiency in humans (Cakmak, 2012). Zn is necessary for the metabolic activities of all living things, including microbes, plants, and animals. "Hidden hunger" refers to an insufficiency of certain micronutrients, such as Zn, iron, and others (De Valença et al., 2017). Zn is needed in small amounts for living organisms, but it is just as vital as other nutrients. Zn deficiency is just as significant as iron and vitamin A deficiency in terms of risk factors for global health (Salgueiro et al., 2000, Hotz, 2007, Palmgren et al., 2008). A significant amount of fertile land is affected by the Zn shortage, and due to inadequate Zn intake, approximately one-third of the total population experiences Zn deficiency (Cakmak, 2002). In agriculture, a variety of chemical fertilizers are applied to reduce the Zn deficiency in the soil for crop production, but they also pollute the environment. Therefore, agriculture needs a feasible alternative which can be important in this situation.

Plant growth-promoting microorganisms (PGPMs) are helpful microbes that supply vital nutrients from the soil to plants and are important to their survival in harsh environments. These microbes are crucial for the production of phytohormones, nutrient cycling, and disease protection in plants in addition to supplying essential nutrients (Gouda et al. 2018, Berg et al. 2009). PGPMs can solubilize and increase the availability of Zn in soil. PGPMs such as *Acinetobacter*, *Arthrobacter*, *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Enterobacter*, *Exiguobacterium*, *Burkholderia*, *Ralstonia*, *Sphingomonas*, *Stenotrophomonas*, *Variovorax*, and *Xanthomonas* have the capability to convert insoluble Zn to soluble form (Fasim et al., 2002, Abaid-Ullah et al., 2015, Anuradha et al., 2015, Khande et al.,

2017, Gandhi and Muralidharan 2016, Gontia-Mishra et al., 2017). These microorganisms employ different types of methods, including oxidoreductive systems on cell membranes, siderophores synthesis, and acidification (Chang et al., 2005, Saravanan et al., 2011). Additionally, these microorganisms synthesize organic acids that can chelate Zn and raise Zn solubility as well as sequester Zn cations (Jones and Darrah 1994). Several studies indicate that PGPMs are important in improving native Zn bioavailability to plants (Hafeez et al., 2013, Abaid-Ullah et al., 2015). In this review, we have discussed the role of PGPMs in Zn solubilization.

PGPMs in other nutrients uptake

PGPMs play an important role in the soil ecosystem and provide various vital nutrients from the soil to plants. PGPMs can fix nitrogen which is a key source of nitrogen for maintaining soil fertility as well as for sustainable agricultural production. The general classification of nitrogen-fixing microorganisms is (a) symbiotic, which includes microbes from the Rhizobiaceae family that symbiotically grow with leguminous plants like *Rhizobium*, *Mesorhizobium*, *Sinorhizobium*, and *Allorhizobium*, and non-leguminous plants such as *Frankia* and (b) non-symbiotic such as *Cyanobacteria*, *Azospirillum*, *Herbaspirillum*, *Clostridium* and *Azotobacter* etc. (Ahemad and Khan 2012, Bhattacharyya and Jha 2012). In specialized formations called nodules, symbiotic microorganisms alter the morphological and physiological characteristics of soil microbes and plant roots (Unkovich et al. 2008). Non-symbiotic nitrogen-fixing microorganisms can fix nitrogen in small amounts (Glick 2012). PGPMs that can fix nitrogen are crucial to the health of plants and the soil. Up to 65% of the total nitrogen used in agriculture is believed to come from biological nitrogen fixation, largely by PGPMs, and this process will become more and more important in the future for managing plant nitrogen. (Matiru and Dakora 2004).

PGPMs convert phosphorus insoluble form into soluble form and make it readily available to plants. There are several studies which demonstrated that PGPMs aid in phosphorus uptake and enhance crop production (Sawers et al. 2017, Wu et al. 2012). PGPMs are capable in phosphorus solubilization by using different types of mechanisms such as the synthesis of organic acids, and enzymes. The secretion of organic acids by microorganisms is mostly regulated by genes although environmental factors may also have an impact (Li et al. 2016). Several types of organic acids such as acetic acid, gluconic acid, glucuronic acid, butyric acid, fumaric acid, citric acid, lactic

acid, propionic acid, succinic acid, oxalic acid, and valeric acid are produced by PGPMs. Organic acids' role in phosphorus solubilization is frequently linked to their ability to reduce pH levels and their cations' chelating abilities (Zeroual et al. 2012, Behera et al. 2017). Another mechanism that contributes significantly is phosphorus mineralization by PGPMs. Phosphorus-hydrolyzing enzymes synthesized by microorganisms, such as phytase and phosphatases, play a significant role in governing the mineralization process (Sato et al. 2015).

Through a variety of processes, including the production of inorganic and organic acids, acidolysis, and chelation, PGPMs, including bacteria, fungus, and actinomycetes, can dissolve the insoluble potassium from soils (Archana et al. 2013, Gundala et al. 2013, Keshavarz Zarjani et al. 2013, Saha et al. 2016). Potassium solubilization by PGPMs promotes plant development and crop production (Ahmad et al. 2016, Bakhshandeh et al. 2017, Xiao et al. 2017). Several researchers have shown that plant species' germination, seedling vigour, growth, yield, and plant uptake of potassium were all generally improved in greenhouse and field conditions by inoculating seeds and seedlings with PGPMs (Anjanadevi et al. 2016, Awasthi et al. 2011, Lynn et al. 2013, Zhang and Kong 2014). By enhancing the physical and chemical properties of the soil and secreting several hormones that promote plant growth and development, PGPMs not only aid in the solubilization of insoluble potassium but also boost plant biomass (Bakhshandeh et al. 2017).

Importance of Zn

Zn is one of the most significant elements that functions as a prosthetic group in proteins. It is essential for the production and metabolism of biomolecules like protein, lipids, and carbohydrates as well as for enzyme activities involving RNA polymerases, superoxide dismutase, and other molecules (Sharma et al., 2013, Cakmak and Kutman 2018). Zn deficiency is stated as the major risk factor for humans due to its remarkable properties. Many health concerns, such as growth problems, skeletal deformities, difficulties healing wounds, an increased chance of miscarriage, and diarrhoea, have been related to Zn deficiency (Salgueiro et al., 2000). The crop production is inhibited by the lack of native soil Zn, which also has an impact on human health (Cakmak 2008, White and Broadley 2005). Zn is present in soils in many forms, including exchangeable forms, biologically complex forms, carbonate-bound forms, minerals adsorbed on clay, and occluded in sesquioxides (Han et al., 2011, Ramesh et al., 2014).

In addition to being needed for the manufacture of protein and chlorophyll, enzyme activation, oxidation reactions, and metabolism of carbohydrates in plants, Zn is also necessary for carbonic anhydrase function (Xi-wen et al., 2011, Hussain et al. 2018). Moreover, the absence of Zn slows down several activities including photosynthesis and the production of biomolecules which lowers the crop's quality (Xi-wen et al., Efe and Yarpuz 2011). Zn fertilizer application has thus become essential for raising crop quality and productivity. Several countries, including China, Iran, Pakistan, Turkey, and India, have large areas of soil that are poor in Zn, which causes the effects of Zn deficiency in the people of those particular areas (Cakmak and Kutman 2018, Upadhayay et al., 2019). Inadequate Zn solubility in the soil is one of the primary causes of Zn shortage in crops (Upadhayay et al., 2018, Upadhayay et al., 2022).

PGPMs in Zn solubilization

Plants absorb a limited amount of Zn in the form of divalent cations because small amount of the total Zn is found in soluble form in agricultural soil. One of the most prevalent micronutrient deficits is Zn deficiency, which results from problems with soil Zn availability. There are many techniques that have been used for a long time to treat Zn deficiency. To increase the amount of Zn in plants different agronomic techniques are employed such as applying chemical fertilizers to the soil. Zn sulfate has been employed as Zn fertilizers but their use puts pressure on the economy and the environment and after seven days of fertilizer application it turns into insoluble forms (Rattan and Shukla 1991). Other techniques have been employed to encourage plants to uptake Zn, including crop rotation, traditional breeding, transgenic techniques, and genetic engineering (Gustin et al., 2009, Cakmak et al., 2010, Mhatre et al., 2011, Tan et al., 2015). Plant breeding methods are used in agriculture from several years to produce plants with sufficient value of Zn and other nutrients. However, there are some advantages and some limitations of these methods. These methods are profitable, laborious, costly, feature ethical issues, unfriendly to the environment, and inapplicable in economically backward countries (Mayer et al., 2008, de Santiago et al., 2011). Therefore, there is a need for a useful, environmentally acceptable alternative in agriculture that also improves plant nutrient content. Scientists and researchers are concentrating on PGPMs in this area since they are crucial for improving plant growth and enhancing the nutritional content of plants.

Figure 1. PGPMs in Zn and other nutrient uptake and plant growth and development

PGPMs are beneficial microorganisms are mostly found in the rhizosphere zone where they colonize and exhibit a variety of traits related to plant growth. These microorganisms both directly and indirectly help in the growth of plants. In direct methods, these microorganisms help in the uptake of nutrients, release organic acids and enzymes, and modulate the phytohormone levels in plants. Indirect methods include the synthesis of secondary metabolites which control pathogens and compete for nutrients with other microbes. PGPMs have numerous characteristics that promote plant growth, solubilize Zn in the soil, and make it easier for it to move from the soil environment to different plant tissues (fig 1) (Shakeel et al., 2015). The ability of PGPMs to make plants nutrient-rich demonstrates their potential that makes plants combat Zn deficiency and reduces Zn malnutrition. This method of biofortification which includes agronomic and biotechnological techniques is economic and environment- friendly and increases agriculture production without

any chemical application in agriculture (Upadhayay et al., 2018). The usage of PGPMs, which has several qualities that encourage plant growth, offers a sustainable approach for producing biofortified crops and enhancing production (fig 1) (Upadhayay et al., 2022a). PGPMs evaluated under in vitro conditions exhibited remarkable Zn solubilization properties and had growth-stimulating effects on plants, making it a promising bio-inoculant to increase plant Zn content (Vaid et al., 2014, Kamran et al., 2017).

The important reason for the Zn solubilization is that PGPMs secretes certain types of organic acids, which acidify the soil and cause Zn to become converting in soluble forms because of the lowered pH (Ramesh et al., 2014, Rehman et al., 2021). The secretion of organic acid by PGPMs plays a major role in Zn solubilization. Organic acids such as 2-ketogluonic acid and gluconic acid are produced by PGPMs (Fasim et al., 2002). Another reason is the production of chelating substances like siderophores that are important for Zn, iron and several other micronutrients solubilization. (Saravanan et al., 2011). PGPMs produce different types of siderophores that can be divided into distinct categories the hydroxamate type (also known as "ferrioxamine B"), the carboxylate type (also known as "rhizobactin"), and the catecholate type (also known as "enterobactin") (Matzanke, 2017). Producing siderophores and proton, oxidoreductive systems on cell membranes and chelated ligands are some other pathways that could be implicated in the solubilization of Zn (Wakatsuki 1995. Chang et al., 2005). Several types of microorganisms such as *Pseudomonas*, *Rhizobium*, *Bacillus*, and *Azospirillum* are used to improve Zn content of plants (Table 1) (Rana et al., 2012, Hussain et al., 2015).

Additionally, PGPMs are living transformers that convert inaccessible forms of Zn into available forms, their usage as an alternative to chemical fertilizers should be promoted (Rana et al., 2012, Singh et al., 2017). Currently, PGPMs are utilizing as an environmentally acceptable and productive bio-inoculant to provide enough Zn to the edible portions of crops.

Table 1. Different types of PGPMs in Zn solubilization and plant growth

S. No.	Microorganisms	Host	Result	Reference
1	<i>Serratia liquefaciens</i> , <i>S. marcescens</i> and <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	Wheat	PGPMs increases wheat's Zn content and grain production	Abaid-Ullah et al., 2015
2	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	Soybean and wheat	Enhanced seed yield and Zn concentration in seeds	Khande et al., 2017
3	<i>Pseudomonas fragi</i> , <i>Pantoea dispersa</i> , <i>Pantoea agglomerans</i> , <i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> and <i>Rhizobium sp.</i>	Wheat	Roots and shoots' Zn content increased	Kamran et al., 2017
4	<i>Burkholderia cepacia</i> and <i>Pantoea rodasii sp.</i>	Paddy	Increased the growth and production, and raised the Zn content of rice grains	Upadhayay et al., 2022
5	<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	Wheat	Increased plant height, chlorophyll, grain number and Zn content in grain	Joshi et al., 2013
6	<i>Azospirillum</i> , <i>Pseudomonas</i> and <i>Rhizobium sp.</i>	Wheat	Increased Zn in whea	-
7	<i>Bacillus aryabhatai</i> strains	Soybean and wheat	Increased plant growth and Zn	Ramesh et al., 2014

			assimilation in seeds	
8	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	Maize	Solubilized Zn and plant growth promotion	Hussain et al., 2015
9	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	Wheat	Increased biomass and Zn contents in wheat grains	Javed et al., 2018
10	<i>Burkholderia sp.</i> and <i>Acinetobacter sp.</i>	Rice	Increased growth attributes and yield and total Zn uptake	Vaid et al., 2014
11	<i>Exiguobacterium aurantiacum</i>	Wheat	Enhanced Zn and Fe in grain and also enhanced N, P, and K concentration	Shaikh et al., 2017
12	<i>Alcaligenes sp.</i> , <i>Bacillus sp.</i> , and <i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	Maize	Zn contents increased	Bashir et al., 2021
13	<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	Okra	Enhanced Zn content in Okra	Karnwal 2021a
14	<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i> VBZ4 and <i>P. stutzeri</i> VBZ17	Tomato	Enhanced plant growth and development and higher Zn content in tomato fruit	Karnwal 2021
15	<i>Rhizobium tropici</i> and <i>B. subtilis</i>	Common bean	Increased biomass, grain yield and Zn accumulation in plant	Jalal et al., 2021

Conclusion

Zn is important for every living organism and to overcome its deficiency in humans we need to grow crops which are rich in Zn. Modern agriculture focuses on increasing crop yield and producing crops that are enriched with nutrients. There are several techniques used in agriculture to raise the Zn content of crops, including applying Zn fertilizers, crop rotation, and using genetically engineered crops and others, but these techniques are expensive, time-consuming, and labour-intensive. Therefore, using PGPMs in agriculture is a sustainable and environmentally friendly approach and can be used as an alternative to these methods. PGPMs provide several essential nutrients to plants which are important for plant growth and development. PGPMs provide Zn from soil to plants by using several mechanisms such as producing organic acids, chelating substances and enzymes, which play important roles in Zn solubilization.

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